

ERGASH JUMANBULBUL UGLI HOUSE MUSEUM

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the life and work of Ergash Jumanbulbul, the founder of the Kurgan school of epics, the process of establishment and history of the house museum, activities, exposition, and exhibits.

Key words: home museum, bakshi, art, culture, performance, tradition, epic, term, school of epic, exhibit, bakshi.

ERGASH JUMANBULBUL O'G'LI UY MUZEYI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola Qo'rg'on dostonchilik maktabi asoschisi Ergash Jumanbulbul o'g'lining xayoti va ijodi, uy muzeyining tashkil etish jarayoni va tarixi, faoliyati, ekspozitsiyasi, ekspozatlar haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: uy muzey, baxshichilik, san'at, madaniyat, ijro, an'ana, doston, terma, dostonchilik maktabi, ekspонат, baxshi.

ДОМ-МУЗЕЙ ЭРГАША ДЖУМАНБУЛЬБУЛЯ УГЛИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о жизни и творчестве основоположника курганской эпической школы Эргаша Жуманбюльбуля, процессе создания и истории дома-музея, деятельности, экспозиции, экспонатах.

Ключевые слова: дом-музей, бакши, искусство, культура, спектакль, традиция, эпос, термин, эпическая школа, экспонат, бакши.

Bakhshi art is a kind of art that has been cherished among the people since time immemorial. Since ancient times, at weddings, public gatherings, and various gatherings, bakhshis accompanied the sound of drums, sang epics and thermas, and parties with such oral songs lasted for a long time. Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli, the famous Uzbek folk poet, the founder of the Korgon school of epics, was born in 1868 in the family of a peasant epic in the village of Korgon, Koshrabot district, Samarkand region. Since the 17th - 19th centuries, Bakhshi's descendants, such as Yodgor, Lafas, Mulla Tosh, Mulla Kholmurod, Jumanbulbul, Tilla old lady, Sultan old woman, Jossoq, Yorlakab, etc., became famous epic poets. Ergash received his epic education from his father Jumanbulbul. In 1884 - 1886, he studied at one of Bukhara's madrasas, studied Persian and Arabic languages and practiced husnikhat.

Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli's "Kuntugmish", "Yakka Ahmed", "Alibek with Bolibek", "Dalli", "Ravshan", "Kunduz with Star", "Khaldorkhan", "Girl Jibek", "Hasankhan", "Avazkhan", "Avaz's trip to Farang", "Nurali", "Khiromon" ("Jahangir"), "Alpomish", "Yusuf bilan Ahmed", "Tulumbi", "Kironkhan", "Kumri", They could recite 50 epics such as Ashiq Gharib, "Uzro with Vomiq", "Gulshah with Varka", "Mahtumkuli", some of the bakhshis only recited epics, some of them also created epics themselves. [1]

Of these, the first 9 epics, the content of the epic "Oysuluv", many traditional and modern terms, information about the bakhshis that passed before him and the art of epic writing were recorded by the Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli himself. Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli knew examples of all genres of folk epics. He fought for the idealism, nationalism, and artistic beauty of epics. His epic "Biography", "Tashkent tariff", "Kizil", "Tursunoy", "Okhunboboev", "Ghozi Olim", "Otajon Khashim", "Poets leader Khodi", "Eshon", "Asov", "Girls", "It's been a week, it's raining" are noteworthy.

He read the works of Navoi, Fuzuli, Hafiz, Bedil, Mashrab, Mahtumquli. However, due to financial difficulties and the death of his father, he could not continue his studies. Returning to his village, he studied independently and improved his skills in epic writing. For some time, he collected cafsan from the peasants with the help of his school teacher and father-in-law Tamurod Khatib. In 1887-1889, Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli worked as a mirza (secretary) of Kozibekka, one of the landowners of the Nurota Begiya belonging to the Bukhara Emirate. He lived in prison from 1904-1905. In 1912-1922, he worked as a healer, told stories, and sang epics in the villages around Bulungur, Gallaorol, Urgut districts, Jizzakh and Panjakent. After returning to his village in 1923, he opened a one-room school in the village of Karakisa in 1924. He came to Samarkand in 1925. In 1926-1928, in the village of Kirkshodi, Bulung'ur district, Polkan poet, Fazil Yuldosh, together with his son, was engaged in writing and writing down his memorized epics. In 1929-1936, Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli was mainly engaged in agricultural work in his village, and continued to train students in epic poetry. Arriving in Tashkent in 1936, until April 1937, folklorist He lived in H. Zarifov's house. At the end of April 1937, he returned to his village and died in the hands of his grandson Abdughani in the village of Pastkoshtangali.

After Bakhshi's death, the study of Bakhshi's work decreases for a while. But in 1970, Aydin Sindarov, a village teacher from the generation of Bakhshi's, Ergash Jumanbulbul, studied the work of his son and the work and activities of Bakhshis, and started to organize home museums of Bakhshi's. For this purpose, Ergash succeeds in finding tools, clothes, and exactly Bakhshi's drum belonging to Bakhshi and used by Bakhshi. Later, Aydin Sindarov diligently collected items belonging to that period from the surrounding villages such as Karakissa, Koshtangali, Chinor. Among the items, there is a tilakori zirak worn by Bukhara women, a spinning wheel, and a hand mill for grinding grain. In May 1972, the 100th anniversary of the poet's birth was widely celebrated. During this period, the statesman Sharof Rashidov, who was well acquainted with the work of Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli and served as the head of the state for many years, visited the village of Kurgan in 1978. In the village, he created a garden on an area of more than one hectare, moved the grave of Bakhshi, built a mausoleum with a large dome, and installed a statue of Bakhshi in the garden. During this period, the house museum was given the status of "People's Museum". [2]

In addition, in the city of Samarkand, a complex statue was erected to the son of Ergash Jumanbulbul, the poet Islam, the poet Polkan, and Fazil Yuldosh ugli. A garden in

Nurota district, a school in Koshrabot district, and streets in Tashkent and Samarkand cities were named after the poet. Over the years, the museum building fell into disrepair because it was made of clay.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Museums”, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Museums” [3] of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 12, 2010, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 On five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 State program on the implementation of the strategy of actions in the “Year of communication with the people and human interests” and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further develop and improve the sphere of culture and art” [4] PD-4947 of 11/2017 “About the approval of regulatory and legal documents” necessary for the implementation of the December Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the complex program of measures to improve the activities of state museums and strengthen the material and technical base in 2017-2027” [5] No. 975 with the decision No. 68 confirmed. Pursuant to paragraph 8 of the regulation and the letter of the Ministry of Culture dated October 22, 2019 (01-11-10-23 No. 60), the governor of Samarkand region, The Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli memorial museum should be established as a branch of the Samarkand state museum-reserve. The opening ceremony of Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli memorial museum was held on April 2, 2020. The museum was transferred to the management of the Samarkand region reserve department. Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli home museum is located inside the Koshrabot recreation park, in the garden there is a statue of Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli, a house museum building, and a grave. The total area of the house museum is 1.82 ha, the exposition area is 0.0473 ha, and 144 objects are stored in the house museum fund. There are 105 objects in the museum.

In the entrance hall of the museum, there are exposition halls, fund, and on the walls of the doors leading to the museum director’s room, there are pictures of male and female bakhshes singing epics, and decisions made by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

1. In the exhibition hall. In the upper part of the exhibition hall, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev’s words, “ It is worth it to be proud of the fact that Uzbek philanthropy has given the world such famous representatives as Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli, Islam poet, Fazil Yuldosh ugli, Polkan poet, Bola bakhshi, Esemuratjirov, Sherna bakhshi, Mardonaqul Avliyokul oguli, Kadir bakhshi Rahimov. In the room, there is a book of epics written by Ergash Jumanbulbul’s ugli, such as “Nightingale”, “Aminovul Sayings”, “Treasure of Wisdom”, “Kunduz ulan Yulduz”, “Kuntugmish”, “Ravshan”, genealogies of Ergash Jumanbulbul’s ugli descendants, family, and generations of artists. , besides other bakhshs, a portrait of the poet Islam Nazar’s ugli, brief information about the bakhsh, epics such as “Oyjamol”, “Gulikhiromon”, “Gulshan Bog”, “Alpomish”, a portrait of Fazil Yuldosh ugli “Murodkhan”, “Rustam”, “Selected works” , portrait of Polkan, Muhammadgul Jonmurad ugli, M. Afzalov’s epics such as “Polkan Shair”, “Birth of Goroguli”, “Alpomish”, “Khasankhan”, “Dastagul”, portrait of Egamberdi Ollamurod’s ugli, “Aysuluv”, “Bakhrom and Gulandon” , epics such as “Khaldorkhan”, a portrait of Rahmatullah Yusuf’s ugli, Ulkan Kissakhan Bakhshi’s book “Rahmatullah Yusuf’s ugli” and Bakhshi’s “Birth of Gorogli” trade union membership card, etc.

2. In the exhibition hall. Personal belongings of Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli: chest, comb, wallet, khum belonging to the late 19th-20th century found in the Khoshrabot region, dombira

belonging to the 20th century, family tree of the “Kurgan” epic school, Ergash Jumanbulbul ugli and poet Polkan, Egamberdi Ollamurod ugli , ethnographer There are exhibits such as the process of recording epics from the son of Mukhamadali Koshmakov Egamberdi Ollamurod, photographs depicting the creative activities of such poets as Qilich Bakhsh Shukurov, Fazil Yuldosh ugli and Islam poet, and local men’s and women’s costumes of the 20th century.

3. In the exhibition hall. There is a closed top that reflects the 20th century. The most valuable exhibit in the exhibition hall is the rice bowl belonging to Ergash Jumanbulbul. There are exhibits such as sandals, blankets, rice, tablecloths, pillows, teapots, bowls, wooden trays, chests, embroidery, as well as 20th-century household items such as a copper oven, a kettle, a plate, a wooden plate, a spoon, a ladle, and a spoon. , there are exhibits such as a spinning wheel.

4. In the exhibition hall. Among the historical areas of Koshrabad district, there are places such as Fazilman Lake, Tosh Etmas Koya, Chashmai Zirak, madrasa textbooks of the 19th century, exhibits such as pencils, inkwells, water bottles, whips, horse saddles, ceramic jugs, khum, kavush, khassa, sticks, and the works of Ergash Jumanbulbul’s ugli. There are exhibits such as pictures of researching folklorist scientists, the book “Uzbek folk art” consisting of 11 volumes, photo plates from the celebration of the 100th anniversary of Ergash Jumanbulbul’s son in 1978, and published articles and books about Ergash Jumanbulbul’s ugli.

In conclusion, it can be said that Ergash Jumanbulbul son house museum is well organized. But since the museum is located far from the city and district center, there is not much flow of local and foreign tourists. Therefore, tourists coming to Nurota Shahri from foreign countries pass through Josh by bus. It is necessary to install a large sign pointing to the museum in the village of Joshdan Kurgon and attract tourists.

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